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FUNDING INCONGRUENCE:
AN OVERVIEW OF THE DISCONNECT
BETWEEN LOCALLY LED ORGANIZATIONS
& INTERNATIONAL FUNDERS
FOR WASH PROJECTS

2025

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*Created by the EcoCiv Water Team
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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations

CRS-Catholic Relief Services
CSO - Civil Society Organization
DAC - Development Assistance Committee
ED - Equivalency Determination
ER - Expenditure Responsibility
EU - European Union
GDP - Gross Domestic Product
IDA-International Development Assistance
INGO - International Non-Governmental Organization
LLO - Locally led Organization
MDB - Multilateral Development Banks
NGO - Non-Governmental Organization
O & M - Operations and Management
ODA-Official Development Assistance
OECD - Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
PPP - Public-Private Partnership
SDG - Sustainable Development Goals
UN - United Nations
UNDP - United Nations Development Programme
UNHCR - United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF - United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
USAID - United States Agency for International Development
WASH - Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene

WASH Landscape Study

Executive Summary

Access to clean water and sanitation is fundamental to sustainable development, yet over 5.5 billion people worldwide still lack access to safely managed drinking water. Countries on the African continent face some of the most severe WASH (water, sanitation, and hygiene) challenges, where over 400 million people lack basic drinking water services. Locally led organizations (LLOs) are critical in addressing these challenges by leveraging their deep understanding of community needs. However, systemic barriers—including funding challenges, market access, and organizational capacity—severely limit LLOs ability to sustain and scale their efforts.

This study examines the financial and structural challenges LLOs face in Africa’s WASH sector, focusing on Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda. Key findings highlight that while international funders increasingly recognize the value of locally led development, less than 10% of civil society aid reaches Global South organizations. LLOs struggle with limited access to funding networks, complex compliance requirements, and a lack of resources for long-term capacity building. Meanwhile, funders often prioritize established partnerships and face challenges in identifying and supporting smaller, emerging LLOs.

A central theme that emerged from this research is the disconnect between funding structures and local needs. While funders emphasize impact measurement and financial accountability, LLOs operate in complex, resource-constrained environments where rigid funding models often fail to support long-term sustainability. The challenge is about increasing financial resources and rethinking how funding is structured and supporting local solutions—shifting toward models that prioritize trust, flexibility, and equitable partnerships. Addressing this gap is critical to ensuring that WASH interventions are effective and sustainable.

1. Introduction

Access to clean, safe, and affordable water is essential for human livelihoods and the planet's health. Often referred to as the "great enabler," water is a foundational driver of sustainable development, underpinning many of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Ensuring universal access to clean water and sanitation is the core objective of SDG 6. Yet, as of 2023, more than 5.5 billion people still lack access to safely managed drinking water, while over 4 billion people lack access to safely managed sanitation services.¹

When reviewing water security globally, Africa faces the most severe challenges in Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH), with over 400 million people lacking basic drinking water services.² Systemic issues such as climate change, shifting agricultural practices, deforestation, and persistent gender inequalities exacerbate these challenges. In response, numerous locally led organizations (LLOs), including non-profit and for-profit organizations, across Africa address these issues through community-driven, integrated approaches, drawing on their deep understanding of local contexts.

While their passion for creating meaningful change within their communities drives locally led organizations, they face significant barriers to sustaining their efforts. Challenges such as securing international partnerships, accessing consistent funding, and navigating funder-driven priorities hinder their capacity to retain skilled staff, stay current on technical advancements, attract collaborators, and effectively manage their resources.

Despite the potential to create a transformative impact, these financial and systemic barriers often limit the scale and sustainability of locally led organizations. This study examines these challenges in the WASH sector, focusing on how funding inequities and structural barriers impact the effectiveness of LLOs in Africa. By identifying these constraints, we aim to highlight pathways for more equitable support systems that empower these vital actors in achieving universal water and sanitation access.

¹ MacAlister et al., "Global Water Security 2023 Assessment."

² UNICEF, "Africa to Drastically Accelerate Progress on Water, Sanitation and Hygiene – Report."

1.1. Context

Localization refers to shifting decision-making power and funding control to local actors rather than international intermediaries. Studies, such as *Passing the Buck: The Economics of Localizing International Aid*, have shown that in the four countries examined, local and national organizations (LLOs) were, on average, 17% more cost-effective than larger international organizations in delivering assistance.^{3,4} This efficiency stems from their deep community knowledge and lower administrative costs. Localization, also known as locally led development, is increasingly recognized as a sustainable and cost-effective approach for humanitarian aid, public health, WASH interventions, and broader development efforts.

This shift toward decolonizing aid and prioritizing local leadership acknowledges the ethical imperative of empowering communities to take a central role in their development. Initiatives like the Grand Bargain, introduced in 2016, aimed to localize 25% of funding from top aid agencies (including the EU, USAID, and UNHCR) by 2020. However, this goal was far from met, with only 3.4% of funds in 2020 reaching LLOs.⁵ To address this, the Grand Bargain was renewed as "Grand Bargain 2.0" in 2021, with participants, such as the EU, committing to a roadmap to achieve the 25% localization target by the end of 2024.

Organizations are testing various strategies to meet localization targets. For example, USAID has set ambitious goals: by 2025, directing 25% of its funding to local actors, and by 2030, ensuring that at least half of its programs integrate local actors into leadership roles, such as priority setting, activity design, and results measurement. Meeting these goals requires a fundamental shift in traditional norms, power dynamics, and funding processes while supporting local organizations in building capacity for organizational management, reporting, and monitoring and evaluation.

Despite these commitments, major barriers persist. In September 2024, signatories of the Grand Bargain highlighted ongoing challenges in implementing localization strategies (see Table 1 below). These challenges are twofold: first, internal misalignments within international agencies often hinder effective handovers to local organizations. Second, LLOs face unclear expectations and inconsistent guidance on the criteria required to access these funds. These findings emphasize the urgent need for systemic changes to strengthen the capacity and sustainability of LLOs.

³ Venton and Lang, "There Is a Clear Financial Case for Localizing Aid."

⁴ Venton et al., "Passing The Buck – The Economics of Localizing International Assistance."

⁵ Green, "Why the 'Grand Bargain' Failed to Deliver Its Promise of Local Funding."

Table 1: Reported challenges adapted from The Grand Bargain September 2024 Report⁶

Improving financial systems	Inadequate financial systems hinder accurate tracking and reporting of funds to local and national actors.
Implementing operational changes	Shifting processes and operational practices pose significant challenges and require time to implement effectively.
Navigating policy constraints to reach the target	Sometimes, a lack of clear policies hampers progress toward targets. Meanwhile, counterproductive policies, including increasing compliance requirements from funders, pose significant barriers for local and national actors in accessing funding, particularly with audit report requirements by funders.
Strengthening capacity	Persistent challenges in capacity building, due diligence, and expertise crucial for fund allocation must be addressed. Partner capacity development struggles, especially in linking with specialized institutions for coherent partnerships.
Risk sharing	Identifying strategies to better manage and distribute risks along the funding chain, particularly concerning funders' contributions, is key to effective operations.

One of the most significant challenges is the persistent inequity in funding allocation by major international funders. A 2024 report from the #ShiftthePower movement sheds light on the funding disparities within the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Development Assistance Committee (DAC) donor countries. According to this report, domestic Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in the Global North or International CSOs with offices in-country receive 90% of civil society support from DAC countries. Leaving less than 10% of this funding for local CSOs in the Global South. Despite formal requirements to "partner" with local CSOs, these partnerships often take various forms, many of which do not result in meaningful, direct financial support for the LLOs.^{7,8} This disparity highlights a critical need for reform in funding structures to ensure

⁶ IASC, "3 Pagers on Learning Space Event."

⁷ #ShiftthePower, "Too Southern To Be Funded."

⁸ Miolene, "New Report Reveals Limited Funding for Global South Organizations."

LLOs receive the resources necessary to sustain their efforts and achieve meaningful impact.

The context above represents only a fraction of the international funding landscape. In addition to major funders, numerous small funders, including philanthropic organizations, charities, and development funds, operate with distinct priorities and agendas. This variability further complicates the funding ecosystem, making it fragmented and often inaccessible. As a result, LLOs remain heavily reliant on international aid agencies to fund and deliver projects.

1.2. Purpose

This study - examines the barriers LLOs face in Africa's WASH sector to identify actionable strategies for improving funding accessibility and operational sustainability. The analysis emphasizes organizations in Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda, the locations of the subsequent Capacity Building Project.

1.3. Scope and Objectives

This study explores the challenges locally led organizations face in securing international funding across the Global South. While research encompassed multiple countries, there was a strong emphasis on Ghana, Uganda, and Ethiopia, where the team gathered primary data through the ongoing capacity-building project. The core objectives of this study are to:

- Provide an overview of funding challenges related to localization by summarizing key insights from relevant literature.
- Establish a baseline assessment of the barriers LLOs face when applying for international funding based on quantitative and qualitative data gathered from online surveys and Zoom interviews.
- Analyze the grant-making approaches of international funders by assessing how they provide funding, using data collected through online surveys and Zoom interviews.
- Identify key themes from surveys and interviews to articulate the challenges affecting LLOs and international funders.

2. Landscape Overview (Literature Review)

The scoping review of the literature will support understanding some of the dynamics of the water sector financing and localization through existing data. The aim is to identify all the available challenges for funding the water sector from the literature. This literature review is divided into three sections: the current WASH landscape, the role of locally led organizations, and key stakeholders.

2.1. Current WASH Landscape

A significant portion of the population on the African continent lacks access to safely managed drinking water and sanitation services. Consequently, many African countries are not on track to meet Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6) on water and sanitation. One notable issue is the currency risk associated with financing, as WASH projects generate revenue in local currency while financing is in hard currencies (Euro, USD, GBP). Furthermore, the benefits generated from projects (e.g., improved health) are challenging to quantify and monetize, complicating the translation of investment benefits into revenue flow.⁹

Another notable challenge is the high initial cost. Water infrastructure projects are capital-intensive and require a long development period. Additionally, tariffs for water services applied in most African countries are far below the recovery cost, making it difficult to offset infrastructure construction and maintenance costs. UNDP study highlighted bias on credit rating and higher interest rates for African countries.¹⁰ The African continent ranks lowest in infrastructure default rates at 5%, lower than Asia (6%) and Latin America (10%). However, the overstated perceived risks and elevated cost of capital across the African continent continue to attract less infrastructure investment compared to the other parts of the world.¹¹ Recently (2024), at the Spring meeting of the World Bank and IMF, 40+ African leaders, scientists, international economists, and sustainability experts called for the cancellation of public debt and the transformation of

⁹ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB). Roundtable on Financing water, “Diversifying sources of finance for water in Africa”. 22-23 November 2023.

<https://www.oecd.org/water/background-note-diversifying-sources-of-finance-for-water-in-Africa-10th-rt-meeting.pdf>

¹⁰ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB).

¹¹ Aude Farnault and Khalifa Sarr. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), “Diversifying sources of finance for water in Africa”. 21 August 2024.

https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2024/08/diversifying-sources-of-finance-for-water-in-africa_2b308e53/114791fd-en.pdf

biased credit rating practices, among other reforms. Despite these reforms, there have yet to be significant changes to current policies.¹²

The research conducted by WaterAid revealed that tracing finances to the water sector has been challenging. The lack of transparency in resource flows and the absence of monitoring systems made connecting financial inputs with developmental outputs and outcomes difficult. The unsatisfactory record of these activities does not allow an assessment of equity and efficiency of the investment made at the local level. This makes it more challenging to hold decision-makers accountable for their management of public resources and finances.¹³

As per the donor tracking report, water sector policy and administration management fell 55% between 2018 and 2021, reflecting poor support for the sector.¹⁴ At the same time, the water policies are poorly designed, inefficient, and not targeted. These subsidies benefit the households already connected to the water network, while the most vulnerable continue to face poor access to water points.¹⁵ The water and sanitation sector contributes only 3% of aid focused on empowering women and girls. The other sectors contribute 6%, and the health and education sector contributes 10% to gender equality.¹⁶

The general performance of investment in the water sector needs to improve, with failing systems being the rule rather than the exception. Large infrastructure projects in many African countries are associated with “Big” corruption, including land and water capture. Therefore, the most significant challenges for funding in the water sector are high risk, poor performance, and failing investment.¹⁷

¹² Power Shift Africa and Earth4All. “Stop Africa’s debt crisis from spiraling out of control”. 12 April 2024. <https://earth4all.life/open-letter-africa-debt/>

¹³ WaterAid. “Think Local, Act Local: Effective financing of local governments to provide water and sanitation services”. 2008

¹⁴ Yara Matar, Maura Kitchens West.

¹⁵ Aude Farnault and Khalifa Sarr.

¹⁶ Water Aid, “Essential element: Aid’s continuing and critical role in financing water, sanitation and hygiene”. May 20, 2023.

¹⁷ Teun Bastemeijer. Realites Industrielles, pages 68-71 Editions Institut Mines Telecom. “Water Integrity to close financing gaps in Africa”. August 2019. https://www.cairn.info/load_pdf.php?ID_ARTICLE=RINDU1_193_0068&download=1

2.2. Key Stakeholders

The primary source of development financing for low and middle-income countries is through Official Development Assistance (ODA)¹⁸. In the last five years, ODA spending has generally increased. However, DAC donors have significantly decreased their ODA funding across Africa and Asia since the COVID-19 pandemic. Many global ODA funds are currently directed to Ukrainian refugees and aid, while aid support for developing regions is declining. In 2023, DAC members devoted an average of 0.37 of their gross national income to ODA, a much smaller proportion against the 0.7 target set by the U.N. General Assembly resolution on October 4, 1970.¹⁹

ODA to Africa has been declining, affecting water-related investment. The nature of ODA has changed significantly, with ODA loans exceeding ODA grants. More ODA loans increase the debt burden of already poor-performing economies, making countries more vulnerable. In 2021, 60% of the ODA countries in Africa were lower-middle-income countries. Most funding goes to lower-middle-income countries as compared to lower-income countries. This indicates that lower-income economies face significant challenges in guaranteeing their constituents access to water services.²⁰ The average public debt ratio in Sub-Saharan regions as of 2022, is 56% of GDP, with 19 out of the 35 low-income countries in the region in debt distress or nearly in distress.²¹

¹⁸Official Development Assistance is government aid from official providers to recipient countries that are defined by a specific set of criteria including Gross National Income reported by the World Bank and development status reported by the UN.

<https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/policy-issues/official-development-assistance-oda.html>

¹⁹ Zainab Usman and Tani Washington. "Are the World's Largest Donors Cutting Their Bilateral Aid to Africa?" Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. October 31, 2024.

<https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2024/10/africa-development-aid-oecd-china?lang=en>

²⁰ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB).

²¹ Aude Farnault and Khalifa Sarr.

Figure 1: International Development Association (IDA) aid commitment and distribution²²

According to OECD Catholic Relief Services data, Figure 1 (above), IDA’s aid commitment for Ghana, Ethiopia, and Uganda totaled US\$16.7billion. The total distributed funds totaled US\$12.1 billion. The discrepancy between committed and distributed funds is more prominent country by country, particularly when evaluating the distribution mechanism, whether via grant or loan, as highlighted in Figure 2 (below). In Ghana, the total committed funds for Official Development Assistance (ODA) between 2017 and 2021 amounted to US\$2.9 billion. Of this amount, US\$1.53 billion was distributed. Notably, 100% of the distributed funds were provided as ODA loans, with no allocation as ODA grants. The International Development Association (IDA) accounted for 52.6% of the development finance distribution. Within the overall aid framework, US\$245.17 million (8.4% of total ODA commitments) was allocated to the water sector.²³

²² Figure 1 is adapted from the reported aid for Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda was generated from the International Development Association data from 2017-2021. Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI). ATLAS for Development Finance, 2017-2021. https://aid-atlas.org/profile/international-development-association/uganda/all/2002-2021?usdType=usd_commitment

²³ Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI). ATLAS for Development Finance, “International Development Association to Ghana for All sectors & objectives during 2002-2021”.

Of all three countries, Ethiopia received the highest amount of IDA distribution aid at US\$8.39 billion, along with higher ODA grants (43.6%) compared to Ghana and Uganda. The distribution ratio of development finance from IDA was 78.1%. The share of the water supply and sanitation sector was 9.1% (US\$976mn) of this aid.²⁴

In the case of Uganda, the commitment made was US\$3.1 billion. Of this distributed amount, US\$2.16 billion (representing 70.02%) was allocated as ODA loans, while US\$918 million (29.8%) was provided as ODA grants. The distribution ratio from IDA stood at 70.2% of the total committed funds. Within this aid, the water sector received a dedicated commitment of US\$282.26 million, constituting 9.2% of the total aid allocation.

²⁵

ODA Loan vs. Grant

Data from 2017-2021

https://aid-atlas.org/profile/international-development-association/uganda/all/2002-2021?usdType=usd_commitment

²⁴ Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI).

²⁵ Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI).

Figure 2: Nature of Official Development Assistance²⁶

The most recent data shows WASH funding stood at US\$10 billion in 2021, including DAC donors, non-DAC donors, Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs), private funders, and other multilateral financing. The reduction in WASH funding occurred due to multiple factors like the COVID-19 pandemic, the Russia-Ukraine war, a trade-off between WASH topics, and waning political support for WASH.²⁷ Ironically, aid to the water and sanitation sector fell more rapidly than other sectors during the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic, despite the importance of handwashing and the role of water in controlling infections considering the vaccine inequality.²⁸

ODA grants remain the primary type of grant in Uganda and Ethiopia. In the case of Ethiopia, ODA grants increased in 2015 and only decreased in 2021 due to conflict in northern Ethiopia and COVID-19-related factors. In Uganda, ODA grant contributions have been inconsistent from 2012 to 2021. The World Bank and the United States are Uganda and Ethiopia's two most prominent funders. The World Bank provided more ODA loans (86.9%) than ODA grants (13.1%). The United States has contributed ODA grants primarily to social sectors in the two countries. The water and sanitation sector was not a priority sector in these countries, with an average of 5.8% of cumulative aid contributed to Ethiopia, Kenya, and Uganda.²⁹

²⁶ Figure 2 is adapted from the reported aid for Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda was generated from the International Development Association data from 2017-2021. Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI). ATLAS for Development Finance, 2017-2021.

https://aid-atlas.org/profile/international-development-association/uganda/all/2002-2021?usdType=usd_commitment

²⁷ Yara Matar, Maura Kitchens West. Donor Tracker by SEEK development, "WASH & Sanitation"

<https://donortracker.org/topics/wash>

²⁸ Water Aid, "Essential element: Aid's continuing and critical role in financing water, sanitation and hygiene". May 20, 2023.

<https://washmatters.wateraid.org/publications/essential-element-aids-continuing-critical-role-financing-water-sanitation-hygiene>

²⁹ Development Initiative, "Trends in traditional and non-traditional aid flows to Kenya, Uganda, and Ethiopia". June 2023.

https://devinit-prod-static.ams3.cdn.digitaloceanspaces.com/media/documents/Trends_in_traditional_and_non-traditional_aid_flows_to_kenya_uganda_and_ethiopia.pdf

Figure 3: Total ODA for WASH sector³⁰

In 2021, the top ODA WASH donors were Germany (US\$861 million), Japan (US\$720 million), France(US\$653 million), the EU(US\$537 million), and the US (US\$361 million).³¹ Japan is the only major funder focused on the capacity-building side of the water sector. It supported capacity building through its JICA program by providing training to government institutions and its water bodies.³²

China is Africa's biggest infrastructure and water financier, providing ODA from non-OECD countries. There is a significant difference between Chinese and OECD ODA in scale and nature. China's development assistance is often associated with agreements and concessional and non-concessional loans with a major focus on infrastructure. OECD assistance generally focuses on social development projects in health, water, and sanitation or towards humanitarian aid. Through its International Development

³⁰ Yara Matar, Maura Kitchens West.

³¹ Yara Matar, Maura Kitchens West.

³² Japan International Corporation of Welfare Services (JICWELS). Commissioned by: Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare, Government of Japan. " Report on a Study of International Cooperation in the Water Supply Sector". March 2020.

https://www.mhlw.go.jp/english/policy/health/water_supply/dl/report_2019.pdf

Association (IDA), the World Bank was the largest OECD funder to Africa for water, providing 30% of the investment (2019).³³

Public sector institutions funneled most funds with an average rate of 62.3% in East Africa.³⁴ Private sector financing remains limited in WASH services, accounting for just 2% of finance throughout 2012-2020, primarily in small urban water and sanitation services. The reasons for limited finance include high-risk levels, poor performance, and long payback periods. These risks deter investors who prioritize quick returns.³⁵ Additionally, funders often need to pay more attention to the impact of investing in staff training and logistics. The relevance of WASH projects may be difficult to explain to funders, considering their limited exposure to the challenges of working in the region.³⁶ Public-private partnership (PPP) initiatives mainly focus on large projects with lower transaction costs. The affordability of financial services is a crucial indicator to measure whether consumers and businesses will have access to financial support to improve water and sanitation.

National government budgets for the water sector declined from 20% to 13% of their budget, representing US\$6.1 billion in 2016 to US\$4.3 billion in 2020. Water is an important element in the national development plan. However, the implementation and development of national water investment plans and strategies remain a challenge.³⁷ In the ESAR region, the average government budget was around 27% of their GDP.³⁸ The share of the national infrastructure budget for water and sanitation operations declined to 13% in 2020 from 15% in 2018. Over the years, North Africa and Southern Africa allocated a lower proportion of the total infrastructure budget to Water and Sanitation, the share of Central Africa and West Africa was in line, and East Africa allocated a higher proportion.³⁹ The rising public debt ratio has limited the capacity of African countries to invest in crucial sectors like water and sanitation.⁴⁰

³³ Oliver Jones, Goufrane Mansour, Peter Burr. UNICEF, Oxford Policy Management, AGUA Consult, Bluechain consulting. "THE STATE OF WATER FINANCING IN EASTERN AND SOUTHERN AFRICA". September 2019.

<https://www.unicef.org/esa/media/4971/file/UNICEF-ESARO-2019-WASH-Financing-Regional-Assessment.pdf>

³⁴ Development Initiative, "Trends in traditional and non-traditional aid flows to Kenya, Uganda, and Ethiopia". June 2023. <https://devinit.org/resources/trends-in-aid-flows-to-kenya-uganda-ethiopia/>

³⁵ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB).

³⁶ Faiz Kermani, Sbita Tia Anna Reandi. Dove Press, "Exploring the funding challenges faced by small NGOs". 12 June 2023. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10479561/>

³⁷ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB).

³⁸ Oliver Jones, Goufrane Mansour, Peter Burr.

³⁹ The Infrastructure Consortium of Africa (ICA). "Spending by African Government on Infrastructure" <https://www.icafrica.org/en/topics-programmes/spending-by-african-governments-on-infrastructure/>

⁴⁰ OECD and African Development Bank (AfDB).

According to data from the Fair Water Footprint (Glasgow Declaration)⁴¹ high-income countries heavily rely on Africa’s water resources through trade. An estimated 25% to 33% of the Global North’s total water footprint originates from the African continent, with external water footprints accounting for 50% to 80% of the water consumed in these wealthier nations. This highlights a significant dependency that underscores the uneven distribution of water resources and the hidden impact of global trade on Africa’s water security.⁴²

2.3. Role of Locally Led Organizations

Funding disparity experienced by African NGOs varies between African funders and non-African funders. Local NGOs not only compete with other local NGOs, foundations, and the public sector but also go head to head on the global stage with other INGOs.⁴³ Larger INGOs typically receive and transfer funds, with local NGOs usually serving as implementing partners.⁴⁴

The market for the rural WASH sub-sector is underdeveloped, with informal private sector actors who lack capacity and skill. There is an absence of a regulatory framework in rural areas of many countries to assist in the supply of WASH-related products and services.⁴⁵ In a report, WaterAid argues that “as long as funds for sector projects are retained by the central ministry and projects implemented through the line department, local government capacity to implement water sector projects will not grow.”⁴⁶

Outdated and incomplete rural data creates hurdles to submitting proposals and reports for local operators. Small NGOs struggle to communicate the impact of their project due to the inflexible reporting structures of funding applications, which results in rejected applications.⁴⁷ Smaller non-profit organizations are often excluded from international funding due to needing more social credibility or trustworthiness. It is common for

⁴¹ Fair water footprint resulted from Glasgow Declaration, a partnership comprising government, the private sector, financial institutions and civil society.

⁴² Aude Farnault and Khalifa Sarr.

⁴³ Mosun Layode, Jan Schwier, Siya Hayi-Charters, Maddie Holland, and Soa Andrian.

⁴⁴ Tafadzwa Munyaka, and Angela Umoru-David.

⁴⁵ Oliver Jones, Goufrane Mansour, Peter Burr.

⁴⁶ WaterAid. “Think Local, Act Local: Effective financing of local governments to provide water and sanitation services”. 2008

⁴⁷ Faiz Kermani, Sbita Tia Anna Reandi.

funding to be abruptly withdrawn when an organization is termed non-compliant with funder requirements.⁴⁸

Consideration should be given to the organization's abilities to use assets and capabilities to create scale. Local NGOs are crucial in filling critical service delivery and disaster response gaps. They have the community's trust and possess local knowledge, essential for making an impact. For local NGOs, the community's needs are their shared reality, and they are committed to their communities. Investing in local NGOs generates capacity. Community members lead these organizations to serve their communities and continue to work on solving issues long after international actors have left.⁴⁹

Many research areas, including localization, decolonization in development, racial equity and justice in philanthropy, and 'peer-driven change' highlight the insights into the limited funding reaching African NGOs. Biases, including cultural, racial, and familiarity biases, lead to perceptions of African NGOs as less capable, trustworthy, and accountable than international NGOs (INGOs). This results in low, short-term, or one-off funding, limiting these organizations' ability to develop the necessary capabilities and skills to expand their impact.⁵⁰

In conclusion, the water sector across the African continent faces numerous funding challenges that hinder its development and effectiveness in providing safely managed drinking water and sanitation services. Capital-intensive projects with long development periods characterize the sector. This, coupled with biased credit ratings and high interest rates, creates significant financial barriers to water infrastructure projects. The industry also suffers from poor policy and administration management, lack of transparency in resource flow, and absence of effective monitoring systems. These issues are compounded by a lack of gender focus in a male-dominated industry and the absence of frameworks for rural areas, where the market remains underdeveloped.

Funding challenges are particularly acute, with limited funds reaching local African NGOs and a bias in resource allocation. The situation is exacerbated by outdated or missing rural data, making it difficult to assess needs and effectively allocate resources. Furthermore,

⁴⁸ Tafadzwa Munyaka, and Angela Umoru-David. Inter Press Service, "Fundraising in Africa: How Looking Inward Makes the Difference". 19 Dec 2023.

<https://reliefweb.int/report/world/fundraising-africa-how-looking-inward-makes-difference>

⁴⁹ Mosun Layode, Jan Schwier, Siya Hayi-Charters, Maddie Holland, and Soa Andrian. The Bridgespan Group and African Philanthropy Forum, "Disparities in Funding for African NGOs". July 2021

<https://www.bridgespan.org/getmedia/feed1f9f-bc65-40d6-8614-c880e8720c76/disparities-in-funding-for-african-ngos-report.pdf>

⁵⁰ Layode, Mosun, et al., "Disparities in Funding for African NGOs".

DAC donors have significantly decreased their ODA funding across Africa since the pandemic, with ODA loans exceeding grants. Notably, national government budgets allocated to the water sector have declined, limiting the resources available for much-needed improvements. These multifaceted challenges contribute to the persistent water crisis in Africa, hindering progress towards SDG 6 *Clean Water and Sanitation*. Addressing these issues will require a comprehensive approach, including the involvement of stakeholders across the value chain in inclusive solution design, bottom-up approach, localization, and capacity building of locally led organizations.

The literature indicates that while development finance can catalyze progress, its impact often depends on effective allocation and integration with local priorities. This is reflected in the distribution patterns of ODA in Ghana, where a significant reliance on loans rather than grants may have implications for alignment with local needs and long-term sustainability. Studies have also underscored the importance of targeted sectoral investment, particularly in water and sanitation, for achieving sustainable outcomes. Moreover, research highlights a need for transparency and accountability in aid distribution to ensure equity and effectiveness. However, challenges like dependency on loans and limited grant-based aid persist, raising questions about long-term sustainability and capacity building at the local level.

3. Methods

This section outlines the research processes for participant selection, data collection, and data analysis used to examine the barriers locally led organizations face in Africa’s WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) sector and identify actionable strategies for improving funding accessibility and operational sustainability. The study was conducted simultaneously across two key research streams: one focused on locally led organizations and the other on international funders. This dual focus allowed for a comprehensive analysis of both the perspectives of the organizations on the ground and the priorities of the funding entities supporting them. Surveys and interviews for both research streams occurred between October 2023 and August 2024.

Research Stream 1: Locally Led Organizations

The first research stream focused on locally led organizations operating in Africa’s WASH sector. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining both qualitative and quantitative data collection.

Participant Selection: EcoCiv connected with 43 LLOs from Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda through the following:

- **Word-of-Mouth Referrals:** Existing partners played a key role in identifying potential participants. Referrals were obtained through trusted partner organizations and stakeholders, leveraging their LLOs operating in the region.
- **Networking at Africa Climate Week:** Engagement during Africa Climate Week provided opportunities to connect with LLOs actively addressing water and climate challenges. This enabled direct interactions with organizations, facilitating introductions and further exploration of their work.
- **Referrals from Interviewees:** During interviews conducted as part of the landscape survey and capacity assessment, interviewees recommended LLOs they had previously partnered with or were within their professional networks.
- **Desk Research:** Supplementing the referrals, targeted desk research was conducted to identify additional LLOs. This involved reviewing publicly available data, organizational reports, and other relevant resources to find underrepresented LLOs.

Out of 43 LLO across Ethiopia, Ghana, and Uganda, a subset of 14 were selected by EcoCiv to move forward with interviews based on their technical focus in the WASH sector, their status as a previous Hilton Grant recipient, and their response time to set up an interview.

Interviews: EcoCiv conducted Zoom interviews with 13 locally led organizations. These interviews provided qualitative insights into the various organizational challenges in accessing international funds and their strategies for overcoming funding and operational barriers. The interviews explored funding gaps, capacity challenges, and expectations for partnerships with international funders. The interview questions used for these conversations are outlined in Appendix A. The interviews were recorded after receiving participant consent. A note taker was also present in all interviews to capture the interview minutes. The notes were then analyzed thematically to highlight the gaps, key trends, and challenges in the WASH sector by creating one-pager documents for each interview. The core perceived challenges faced by the interviewees were then fed into OpenAI to collate the themes.

Surveys: Google Form surveys were distributed to over 75 LLOs across Africa and Asia, leveraging an online network of WASH organizations. There were 61 responses; six were discarded as duplicates or lacked enough information. Thus, 55 were viable for data extraction from 13 countries, as highlighted in Figure 4 (below). The surveys consisted of 27 multiple-choice questions and one open-ended question. The surveys collected quantitative data on the broader trends and challenges LLOs face regarding funding accessibility and sustainability. The survey data was used to identify common barriers and variations across regions and organizational types. The questions for the survey can be found in Appendix C.

Figure 4: Number of respondents for the online survey by country (n=55).

In-Person Discussions: EcoCiv conducted site visits with six LLOs for the following capacity-building project. These open-ended discussions allowed the team to gather more in-depth insights into each organization's experiences with international funding and assess their overall capacity. These conversations helped refine the themes emerging from the interviews and surveys.

Research Stream 2: International Funders

The second research stream focused on understanding the perspectives of international funders. This stream aimed to uncover the priorities, challenges, and expectations of funding organizations that support WASH initiatives across Africa.

The first step of collecting data about funders was an online survey designed to gather preliminary quantitative data about the localization of grants. The survey provided information on eligibility criteria, grant sizes and duration, and selection criteria.

Survey design: The survey used a mix of close-ended and open-ended questions to capture details on funding opportunities and procedures for local organizations. The questions are shown in Appendix D.

Participant recruitment: EcoCiv connected with international WASH funders through their granting partner, the Hilton Foundation, and their access to an online WASH network to share the *International WASH Funder Survey* to identify participants. Due to the challenges in accessing international funders, the criteria for selection were based on whether or not the funder had a website and a donation history found online either through Candid or Charity Navigator. Out of 7, six respondents were willing to participate in follow-up interviews.

Data collection and analysis: Google Form surveys were distributed to an international WASH funding network to identify foundations and funders willing to discuss their efforts to localize their funding in the WASH sector. The survey resulted in 7 formal responses. The survey was conducted online and was open for twelve weeks. The responses were analyzed to identify gaps and challenges in recruiting local organizations in the WASH sector as grant recipients. The insights gained from the survey responses informed the design of the funder interviews.

The survey asked funders if they were interested in participating in a 30-45 minute interview. The semi-structured interviews were designed to dive deeper into the funders' experiences identifying and working with LLOs. Interview questions can be found in Appendix B.

Participant selection: Interviewees were identified from the outreach survey. An additional interviewee was determined through the recommendation of a previous interviewee.

Interview structure: There were nine core questions to uncover the funders' grant-making approach. Questions were focused on understanding the continuity of funding beyond the initial funding cycle and reporting and compliance requirements. Additional questions were designed to understand how new recipients were identified, how trust was established, and how the relationship grew. Next, the questions revolved around the challenges LLOs identified in the LLO survey—the questions aimed to understand if those perceived challenges were indeed what hindered grant offerings.

Data collection process: Thirty to forty-five-minute Zoom interviews were conducted with six international funders to gather qualitative data on their funding priorities, decision-making processes, and perceived barriers in supporting locally led organizations. These conversations provided insights into how funders view the sustainability and capacity of LLOs and what factors influence their funding decisions.

Data analysis: The interviews were recorded after receiving participant consent. A note taker was also present in all interviews to capture the interview minutes. The notes were then analyzed thematically to highlight the gaps, key trends, and challenges in the WASH sector.

Analysis: The information gathered from the funder interviews was analyzed alongside the data from the NGO surveys and interviews to identify areas of alignment and disconnect between the two groups. The insights helped clarify the challenges LLOs face in accessing funding and provided actionable strategies for improving the flow of resources to locally led organizations.

4. Findings

The following section presents an overview of the findings from the interviews and surveys conducted with funders and LLOs. First, the interpretation of what a “locally led organization” is presented to identify the gaps between how the two groups discern this key phrase. Second, the findings from the LLO interviews are presented, focusing on the core themes that emerged from the semi-structured interviews. Third, the insights gained from the widespread LLO online survey are presented to complement the findings from the initial interviews. Fourth, the findings from the funder surveys and interviews are presented together.

Our online surveys revealed significant disparities in how different groups define "local organization." When we questioned funders and LLOs about their interpretation of this

term, their responses varied considerably. This discrepancy underscored the diverse viewpoints and conceptualizations of what constitutes a local organization among these key stakeholders. While LLOs emphasize local leadership, governance, and community involvement, funders often focus on financial accountability and legal registration.

Varying Interpretations in Defining a “locally led organization” from the Perspectives of LLOs and Funders

Figure 5: Interpretation of the term “Local Organization” as described by 7 WASH funders and 55 LLOs.

4.1. Results for Research Stream 1: Locally Led Organizations

The findings from Research Stream 1 highlight key themes that emerged from interviews with 14 locally led organizations, particularly challenges related to top-down funding structures. Additionally, the team distributed an online survey to over 75 LLOs to further explore these themes. This survey captured insights into the types of organizations that participated, their difficulties in securing funding, and the challenges of sustaining capacity between funding cycles. This section presents the primary themes identified in the interviews, supplemented by survey data, for a more comprehensive understanding.

Interviews

The core challenges that emerged from the LLOs' interviews were funding and long-term financial sustainability, maintaining organizational capacity, and accessing markets, networks, and resources.

Table 2: Core themes from NGO interviews (n=14)

Core Theme	Secondary Theme	Expressed by # of organizations
Funding Challenges and Sustainability		11
	Short term funding	7
	Difficulties navigating funder requirements	4
	Limited resources for administration/overhead needs	5
Organizational Capacity and Infrastructure		9
	Limited staff numbers, high turnover, and personnel serving multiple roles	4
	Challenges in grant writing, strategies, writing for target audiences, and grant reporting	6
	Challenges with official registration and unclear frameworks	4
Market Access and Resource Constraints		8
	Lack of certifications, logistical issues, or competition	2
	Systemic barriers (e.g., cultural sensitivities, gender-based challenges, language)	5
	Supply chains, resource shortages, and adaptation to	2

	environmental changes	
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Surveys

There were 55 official responses to the survey from 13 different countries. Questions to the online survey can be found in Appendix C. The following findings present a high-level overview of the financial status of the organizations, their challenges in finding and applying for grant opportunities, and other barriers they face in accessing international funding⁵¹.

Financial Status of LLO Survey Respondents

Figure 6: Annual budget range of LLO survey respondents (n=55).

⁵¹ These findings present a snapshot of all of the data collected in this process.

Figure 6 (above) displays the annual budget range of the 55 responding organizations. The majority (65.4%) of these LLOs maintain a yearly budget of US \$50,000- 100,000.

Figure 7 (below) indicates the level of unrestricted and flexible grant opportunities of 55 responding organizations. 73% of these organizations struggle to identify unrestricted and flexible grants. None of these organizations have 100% of their grants as flexible and unrestricted.

Figure 7: Percentage of time flexible and/or unrestricted grant options are found (n=55).

Figure 8: Percentage of grants received through open calls (n=52).

Figure 8 (above) indicates the grants received through open calls. For 51% of responding organizations, out of the total grants received, less than 25% of grants received are through open calls.

“What percentage of the grants you have received are through networking or connections?”

Figure 9: Percentage of grants received through networking and connections (n=53)

Figure 9 (above) indicates the percentage of grants received through networking or connections. Up to 62% of the responding organizations receive the majority (between 50% to 100%) of their grants through networking or connections, indicating the importance of networking opportunities and connections for LLOs.

“How often do you experience difficulties in finding grants to support your organizations projects?”

Figure 10: Difficulties in obtaining grants for projects developed by the organization (n=54).

Figure 10 (above) indicates the difficulty in finding grants that support projects developed by an LLO. 96% of the responding organizations experience difficulty in finding grants that support projects designed and implemented by LLOs. Many organizations experience funding opportunities that have project parameters determined by external sources.

Figure 11: Regularity in adjusting project scope to fit funder requirements (n=54).

Figure 11 (above) indicates the level of adjustment in the project scope to meet the funder's requirements. The majority (64%) of the respondents indicated that they have to adjust their project scope between 50%-100% of the time to align with funder requirements to receive project funding.

Other Barriers

53 out of 55 respondents reported other barriers to accessing international funds. The identified themes identified across these 53 responses were eligibility barriers, limited access to networks and partnerships, and complexity and bureaucracy in the application process.

Organizations face challenges aligning with the eligibility criteria for international funders, which exclude LLOs before they can apply. These particular barriers mentioned by survey respondents include “high budget requirements, long operational history, and the need for specific qualifications.” Limited access to networks (regional and international) and partnerships are also barriers to LLOs.

Additionally, many respondents mentioned the lack of networks or connections with international donors and partners. This barrier is compounded by lacking opportunities for collaborations with larger organizations or the difficulty of finding co-funders to meet donor partnership requirements.

Finally, the application process is often described as cumbersome, involving complicated procedures, extensive documentation, and strict compliance requirements. This creates a significant barrier for organizations that lack the resources or capacity to navigate the process effectively, especially those with limited access to technical expertise or support for proposal preparation.

4.2. Results for Research Stream 2: International Funders

This section summarizes the results from six interviews and seven surveys with international WASH funders, highlighting their geographic diversity, funding priorities, and approaches to supporting locally led organizations. It explores key themes such as funders’ priorities in rural WASH, flexible funding models, and the challenges and barriers to supporting small, local entities. The findings also provide insights into the application processes, risk tolerance, and monitoring strategies that shape how these funders allocate resources in the sector.

Representation

The geographic diversity of the seven funder respondents to the initial survey includes 57% from the USA, 29% from the UK, and 14 % from the EU. Of these, six respondents agreed to an in-depth interview to discuss their funding.

Survey: Understanding the International WASH Funders

Figure 12: Number of funder survey respondents by country (n=7).

Funders Priorities

Many international funders have clear and defined priorities in the WASH sector, while others are more open and flexible with their funding opportunities. Funder-shared priorities include operations and management (O&M) in the rural WASH sector, capacity building, innovative finance, institutional strengthening, locally led organizations, and region/country-specific support. Regularly funded water projects include sanitation infrastructure, water supply infrastructure, local capacity building, O&M, hygiene, water resource management, and system strengthening. 71% of funder respondents support flexible projects focusing on local needs and context.

Funders prioritized organizations that aligned with their organizational objectives. The grants offered vary among funders. Some are project-specific, and others lean towards open and unrestricted. Up to 42% of the respondents strongly believe locally led organizations know what's best for the community and allow flexible or unrestricted funds and flexible project scope to align with the needs of communities.

The support for small, medium, and large organizations varied from funder to funder. Most funders support medium and small organizations. Support for the organizations depended on factors like level of experience, location, visibility, priority countries, communication, and quality of the applications. 3 out of 7 funders spoke about engaging with local

governments and institutions to foster systemic collaboration and create a more comprehensive platform for change.

50% of funders said they prioritize funding to locally led organizations. In comparison, 25% did not prioritize locally led organizations, and 12.5% had funding for locally led organizations as part of their criteria. The remaining 12.5% said their portfolio supports locally led WASH enterprises and grassroots organizations. Only 12.5 % of the funder respondents have goals for allocating funding or a percentage of their portfolio to local organizations, and only one funder revealed the actual allocated percentage.

Funding Local Organizations

Funders' definitions of "locally led organization" vary, encompassing factors such as headquarters location, fund management, leadership composition, board member origins, and legal registration in the operating country.

Figure 13: *Reasons for funding locally led organizations as described by funder respondents*

The reasons for funders to fund local organizations were that it is cost-effective, equitable, sustainable, best suited to deliver context-specific solutions, closest to the most affected communities, and to strengthen in-country capacities. For one funder, the priority was to fund organizations with excellent local presence, knowledge, and capacity and no preference for local or international organizations. In comparison, the reasons for not funding local organizations were grant compliance and the risks associated with co-funding.

Funders identified key barriers to funding local entities: “lack of connections, poor visibility of LLOs, unmet requirements, limited capacity, inadequate applications, insufficient information about their work, unfamiliarity with global best practices, language barriers, organizational size, focus area, absence from major conferences, minimal fundraising efforts, perceived weak impact, lack of US tax-exempt status (e.g., 501(c)3), and the need for funders to navigate expenditure responsibility (ER), and equivalency determination (ED)”.

Almost 60% of funders have priority countries but struggle to find local organizations which operate in those regions. Additionally, a funder expressed that the challenge in supporting small organizations is that they need capacity building, which they cannot provide. A new emerging challenge suggested by a funder was concern over receiving large numbers of fraudulent AI-generated applications.

Funders' risk tolerance for funding local organizations varied significantly. More risk-tolerant funders had flexible criteria, while others maintained stricter standards. Common requirements included 501(c)3 status, annual financial reports, audits, active boards, significant project experience, impact measurement systems, strategic focus, WASH outcomes, and minimum yearly budgets. For 87.5% of funders, these criteria remained consistent across local, regional, and international organizations, though application processes differed for large and small grants.

Application Process

The application process varies from funder to funder. Most of the interviewed funders do not have a solicitation policy, meaning they do not accept open calls. Identifying new non-profits relies on the global North funders network, co-funding, conferences, and occasionally local partner recommendations. For many, the application process starts with concept notes and due diligence. One particular funder uses two different application processes. One is through open calls, and the other is through nomination by grassroots organizations and getting expert judgment on the application. This organization actively wants to fund locally led organizations and allocates weekly office hours for grantees to touch base and discuss grant applications. Another funder has a distinct model of funding that is through internal selection, meaning employees and/or local offices apply for funding to support a specific project, NGO, or individual. 40% of funders expressed they have limited funds, prefer working with existing partners, and do not have space to support new nonprofits.

In the application process, English predominates as the proposal language, presenting ongoing challenges for local organizations due to language barriers. Many funders face constraints in staff capacity and linguistic abilities. A few organizations accept applications in other languages, primarily when they have staff fluent in those languages, such as French. Only one organization accepts applications in multiple local languages, citing operational challenges but a desire for inclusivity. Funders receive anywhere from two to 600 applications annually. Most (62.5%) funders accept applications on a rolling basis, while 12.5% accept every quarter, 12.5% bi-annually, and 12.5% accept internal applications. The proposal's content and quality determine whether an application advances to the next stage.

Typically, funders maintain a 2-3-year funding cycle, often renewing support for existing partners; this leaves little room for new organizations. Limited resources and risk concerns hinder long-term commitments. One funder, however, regularly engages multiple new organizations for short durations. In our research, only one funder committed to extended WASH projects spanning 10+ years, where applicants determine the budget.

Monitoring and Evaluation

The funders prioritized results and assessments over rigorous project oversight. They demonstrate considerable trust in their partnering NGOs, granting them autonomy in tackling the issues. The funders' approach emphasizes trust and flexibility, allowing recipient organizations to manage problem-solving efforts with minimal interference.

Most funders did not conduct regular site visits of the projects. Funders felt it was pragmatic to maintain active communication, receive reports, and minimize their overseas trips.

Gender and Social Requirement

For most WASH funders (75%), gender equity was not a requirement for receiving non-profits. For the remaining 25% of funders, the required parameters included female staff in leadership roles, female staff in total, and females in the communities they serve.

Several funders highlighted that the Global South faces unique challenges in accessing funds, and they want to bridge the gap through capacity building and supporting locally led organizations.

5. Barriers

This study used primary and secondary research methods to identify various obstacles in the funding ecosystem's value chain. The challenges encountered are different based on the stakeholders involved. Some of these barriers are common between LLOs and funders, while others vary significantly. Understanding these barriers is crucial for developing targeted strategies to improve funding access and efficiency. Addressing these barriers will be essential for more equitable access and a compelling funding landscape.

5.1. Barriers LLOs Face in Accessing International Funding

LLOs face systemic challenges that limit their access to funding and long-term sustainability. Weak international networks, low technical capacity, and limited internet access make connecting with funders or participating in global WASH discussions challenging. Many donors favor organizations with international reputations, leaving smaller LLOs struggling with complex proposal writing and application processes. A top-down funding approach often sidelines locally driven solutions, while strict requirements for sub-grant agreements, co-financing, and intermediary organizations from donor countries add further bureaucratic hurdles.

Trust remains a significant barrier, with funders expressing concerns about LLO fund management, the lack of permanent staff, and restricted overhead funding. Additionally, many LLOs lack access to timely information on WASH funding opportunities and face short notice periods for calls for proposals, reducing their ability to compete for grants. Funders' limited understanding of local capacities, geographic challenges, and problem contexts leads to misaligned priorities, while misinterpretations of government policies create unnecessary restrictions.

In some cases, a country's reputation prevents LLOs from receiving support. Lengthy evaluation processes further delay funding, making it even harder for local organizations to sustain their work. Addressing these barriers requires greater donor flexibility, local capacity building, stronger trust-building measures, and more inclusive funding mechanisms that recognize the strengths of LLOs in delivering impactful, community-driven WASH solutions.

5.2. Barriers Funders Face in Aligning with LLOs

Funders supporting WASH initiatives face several challenges in engaging with LLOs, limiting funding opportunities and impact. Many prioritize organizations that closely align with their strategic objectives, making it difficult for new or lesser-known LLOs to gain recognition and secure support. A lack of direct connections and limited representation at major conferences further isolates LLOs, making them harder to identify.

Additionally, LLOs often contend with the perception that their impact is weaker than that of larger, international counterparts. Structural barriers, such as the absence of U.S. tax-exempt status (e.g., 501(c)(3)) and donors' limited capacity to provide direct support, further restrict funding access. The donor landscape relies heavily on Global North networks, co-funding arrangements, and conference-driven partnerships, often reinforcing support for existing partners while leaving little room for new entrants.

Many donors also operate closed funding models, limiting opportunities for unsolicited proposals. Compounding these challenges, the rise of fraudulent AI-generated applications has overwhelmed donors, making it even harder for legitimate LLOs to secure resources and visibility.

5.3. Financial, Governmental, and Systemic Barriers Preventing Alignment between International Funders and LLOs

The WASH sector faces many challenges in adequately bridging the gap between international funding and local implementation. Currency mismatches expose local organizations to financial risks, while the intangible nature of WASH benefits complicates investment appeal. Underpriced water services undermine financial sustainability, and African nations encounter unfair obstacles in global financial markets. The absence of substantial private sector engagement leaves a critical void that international aid struggles to fill.

Governmental and administrative inefficiencies further exacerbate these challenges. Poorly designed and implemented water sector policies, weak administration, and declining national budget allocations—falling from 20% to 13%—have left WASH programs underfunded and ineffective. Transparency in resource flows remains a significant issue, with poor monitoring systems making it difficult to track the allocation of funds and whether they reach the communities most in need. As a result, the most vulnerable populations are often excluded from essential WASH services. Large infrastructure projects are frequently linked to corruption, reducing public trust and

efficiency. In addition, the sector remains male-dominated, with only 3% of aid explicitly dedicated to the needs of women and girls.

On a global scale, official development assistance (ODA) to the African continent has declined, further straining WASH funding. Despite a longstanding commitment by DAC members to allocate 0.7% of their gross national income (GNI) to ODA, contributions have remained significantly lower, averaging 0.37%. Additionally, ODA loans have outpaced grants, increasing the debt burden on recipient countries. Lower-income countries receive disproportionately less support, with 60% of ODA funds going to lower-middle-income nations instead. Many of these funds are channeled through large INGOs, with LLOs primarily serving as implementing partners rather than direct beneficiaries. This top-heavy funding structure limits the ability of LLOs to lead and sustain WASH initiatives.

Systemic barriers further compound these financial and governance issues. Rural WASH markets remain underdeveloped, and data gaps—whether outdated, incomplete, or nonexistent—make it difficult to plan effective interventions. Language barriers continue to create obstacles in accessing funding, navigating complex application processes, and minimal opportunities to engage with international donors. With limited direct funding reaching African organizations, the misalignment between international funders and LLOs persists, preventing the sector from fully leveraging local expertise and leadership. Addressing these barriers requires systemic reforms that prioritize direct funding to LLOs, increase transparency in resource allocation, and promote policies that strengthen local financial and administrative capacities in the WASH sector.

5.4. Research Limitations

This study provides valuable context and illuminates gaps in current knowledge and literature. The following section outlines various limitations that emerged during different phases of the research process.

- **Sample size:** There was a challenge in accessing international funders, resulting in a limited sample size of funders. It was difficult to encourage some funders to participate in the research. A snowballing method was then used to identify more funders; although this granted a few additional interviews, the sample size was still too small to get a representative sample of the funding landscape.
- **Selection process:** Due to the challenges in accessing international funders, the funder representation is skewed, and large funders like USAID, the EU, and USAID contractors like RTI were not included in the interviews or surveys.

- **Diversity bias:** Funder representation is from the global North. There is a complete absence of global South funders in the research due to limited access and information about them.
- **Language bias:** Both funders and locally led organizations that communicate in English were selected for the research, eliminating non-English speaking participants. Those who cannot communicate in English were not part of this research, mainly because of limited resources to engage with them.
- **Stakeholder participation:** The research focused on two main stakeholders: locally led organizations and international funders. This research does not include the role of other stakeholders like governments and private funders.
- **Lack of prior research on this topic:** Due to limited research on the localization of WASH funds, locally led organizations, and funding structure, we were required to develop an entirely new research typology. We used exploratory research rather than explanatory research design. This may result in a limited scope of the analysis. However, it was an opportunity to identify gaps in the current literature.

6. Opportunities and Recommendations

There are identified opportunities and recommendations for LLOs and funders to address the challenges in the current funding landscape and enhance the impact of the WASH sector. The following recommendations are specifically for LLOs and funders to bridge the gap and improve collaboration.

6.1. Locally Led Organizations

There are several recommendations for LLOs based on the funding gaps highlighted in the research. First, LLOs should seek out and take advantage of networking opportunities. LLOs should actively connect with local, national, and international WASH networks for capacity building, networking, and WASH opportunities. Creating peer-to-peer learning networks supports resource sharing and the implementation of best practices.

Second, LLOs should take advantage of and utilize online platforms for learning. There are free courses on M&E, strategy, and project management, all of which can support LLOs growth and capacity. Resource sharing for these online tools regularly occurs within these networking groups. Finally, it is recommended that LLOs develop communication plans to ensure they are “fundable and findable” and evidence of their work is accessible to potential donors. These platforms can be their websites, social media platforms,

conferences, or workshops. Not only does sharing their work more widely increase the likelihood of networking, but it also casts a broader net to connect with potential partners and is a way to share knowledge with different target audiences.

6.2. Funders

The funding gaps highlighted in this research give rise to several recommendations. Given the challenges LLOs face, there is an opportunity for funders to adjust their reporting to better align with LLO's capacities. LLOs have internal governance procedures for financial and M&E reporting. Finding a middle ground between expectations and capacities will enable funders to select impactful LLOs to carry out projects. Additionally, funders can look for opportunities to connect with LLOs by holding local conferences, connecting with their networks, and asking for recommendations. Through this work, it became apparent that LLOs have few opportunities to build their internal capacity sustainably and systematically. Thus, it is recommended that funders explore opportunities to support the capacity-building of LLOs through specific capacity-building funding programs.

6.3. Future Research

This study explores the funding landscape and the challenges locally led organizations face in securing financial support. Future research should further investigate key areas to address knowledge gaps and strengthen the effectiveness of funding strategies.

One critical area for further study is the role of different funders, including private entities, large institutions, and government bodies, in financing the WASH sector. Given the lack of comprehensive research, an empirical examination of funding trends and strategies is necessary. Additionally, there remains a significant disconnect between funders and local organizations. Future studies should explore ways to bridge this gap, ensuring that funders prioritize locally driven solutions and community-based project management while fostering stronger regional collaborations.

Another crucial area of focus is the capacity-building of local organizations. Research should identify effective strategies to enhance their ability to access, manage, and sustain funding. Comparative studies on funding approaches across developing and developed nations could also provide valuable insights into best practices and innovative funding mechanisms. Furthermore, tracking financial flows within the sector remains challenging, with limited transparency and accountability in fund transfers. Future research should explore robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to improve financial oversight and reduce inefficiencies.

6.4. Recommendations

Several recommendations emerged from this study to enhance the funding landscape and improve support for locally led organizations. Strengthening communication between funders and local organizations is essential to overcoming structural, cultural, and geographical barriers that hinder collaboration. Ensuring open dialogue and mutual understanding will facilitate more effective funding partnerships.

There is also a need to increase funding allocations specifically targeting gender disparities within the WASH sector. The research highlighted the limited aid contribution focused on empowering women and girls. It is necessary to increase funding allocations and refocus projects on improving gender balance to rectify the gender disparity within the WASH sector. Additionally, expanding the geographic scope of future studies will provide a more comprehensive understanding of funding dynamics, incorporating a diverse range of funders and locally led organizations.

The shifting landscape of Official Development Assistance (ODA) also warrants closer examination, particularly the decline in aid to African nations and the growing preference for loans over grants. Understanding the implications of these trends is crucial for shaping future funding strategies. Lastly, improving water-related policies and ensuring that vulnerable populations and low-income countries are not left behind should remain a priority. Research should focus on policy frameworks that promote equitable and inclusive development in the sector.

7. Conclusion

EcoCiv's primary research with global North funders and LLOs in Sub-Saharan Africa showed significant disconnects between international funders and LLOs in the WASH sector. These disparities in funding limit the growth and sustainability of LLOs. While LLOs offer cost-effective, community-driven solutions, funding inequities, compliance barriers, and limited networking opportunities hinder their progress. Addressing these challenges requires structural changes in aid allocation, emphasizing direct funding, capacity-building, and more equitable partnerships. Locally led organizations are the key to sustainable, community-driven solutions. Strengthening their capacity and ensuring fair access to resources will drive long-term, impactful change in the WASH sector.

Note as of February 2025: This report was written before the changes in funding associated with dismantling USAID and other development organizations. USAID was a significant source of financing for locally led organizations through multiple pathways (in-country offices, sub-contracts, etc.); the loss of USAID funding and its personnel is catastrophic to international development, human health, and wellbeing. While EcoCiv researched this topic, there are many pathways for agencies like USAID to improve, but in no way does EcoCiv support the dismantling and removal of USAID.

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9. Appendices

9.1 Appendix A - LLO Interview Questions

1. Can you talk us through the projects your organization implements in the water sector (WASH)?
 - a. Follow up: Are there specific programs around water quality testing, increasing water access, or developing community trainings?
2. Who are your direct beneficiaries and/or target groups?
 - a. Follow up: how did you identify these groups?
 - b. How do you work with them? Are they engaged in the project initiation or project maintenance aspects?
3. Do you partner with other local organizations for some projects?
 - a. How do you decide if you need a partner for a project?
 - b. What are your internal criteria for local partners?
4. What are the outcomes of your projects, and how do you measure their success?
5. Could you provide some detail on the number of projects over the past 5 years?
 - a. Follow up: What has their impact been?
 - b. What funders did you work with?
6. Could you provide some information on the history of the organization?
 - a. Follow up: What are your plans for future growth?
7. How do you evaluate or measure the results from your projects?
 - a. Follow up: Do you have any quantitative data you gather and analyze
 - b. How do you measure your projects' impact?
 - c. Do you have an impact model?
8. Are gender, social, and cultural (Faith) inclusion important pieces of your work? If so, how are they integrated into your projects?
9. How does your organization ensure the projects they implement are sustainable?
10. Does your organization include approaches for projects that integrate climate adaptation and mitigation?
 - a. Does it include other aspects? E.g. agriculture, economic empowerment, employment?
11. What have been the biggest challenges and successes over the past 5 years?
 - a. Outside of COVID-19
12. Number of staff
 - a. # of operations/admin
 - b. # of project implementation/managers

- c. # of M&E
- 13. What is your operational budget and what is your project budget? (for a specific project?)
- 14. Are you a registered NGO/Charity within X country? Are you registered in any other countries?
- 15. Do you create annual reports?
- 16. Do you create financial reports? How often are financial reports created and reviewed?
- 17. Do you have an Org chart? Roles and responsibilities.
- 18. What do your partnerships with other LLO, governments, private sectors, etc. look like? What types of contracts do you have in place? (e.g MOUs?)
- 19. What is your current grant strategy?
 - a. How do you find grants?
 - b. What size grants do you apply for?
 - c. Do you have designated staff for grant writing?
- 20. What do your partnerships with other LLO, governments, private sectors, etc. look like? What types of contracts do you have in place? (e.g MOUs?)
- 21. What organizations applied to in the past?
- 22. Obstacles applying for grants (audits etc)?

9.2 Appendix B - Funder Interview Questions

1. Can you broadly talk about your organization's overall grant-making strategy?
2. Some organizations experience challenges in aligning community needs with funder requirements. How does your organization approach these challenges?
 - a. If we have results from a survey—share these results.
3. Long-term funding for WASH projects is hard to secure—what is your organization's experience in providing long-term funding? How does your organization define long-term in terms of funding?
4. How does your organization approach new non-profits? If you were a newly established locally led organization in Ethiopia, with the knowledge YOU have, how would you approach securing funding for your work?
5. How much do you consider the technical writing quality of proposals in your grant making process? Do you make exceptions/considerations for local organizations with non native speakers?
6. How do you ensure a balance of supporting medium and small(emerging) LLO, while maintaining existing support to larger predominantly Western organizations?

7. Do you make efforts to ensure your grant postings reach local organizations that might not have the same resources or awareness to track grants?
8. Is there room for flexibility in criteria of funding, that focus on addressing the cause and not the problem (water security) which differs in each underdeveloped region?
9. Does your organization provide external support when applying for a grant application? This could include pre-application information sessions, feedback for unsuccessful submissions, etc

9.3 Appendix C - LLO Survey Questions

1. Optional: Share the name of your organization
2. Are you formally registered in your country of operation?
3. Where does your organization operate (country and region)?
4. What is the primary language your organization operates in? (If more than one, list them all.)
5. What is your organization's annual budget?
6. What is your annual budget for WASH projects?
7. How often do you reduce your project budget for grant applications to become a more likely candidate?
8. How often do you experience difficulties in finding grants to support your organization's projects?
9. How often do you adjust your project scope to meet funder/donor requirements?
10. How often do you reduce your overhead % to fit grant requirements?
11. How often do you identify unrestricted and flexible grants to apply to?
12. How often do you identify multi-year (2+ years) grants to apply to?
13. Do you find grant applications particularly time consuming and impact your ability to work on project related tasks?
14. How much time do you spend a week on grant applications? (Please provide an estimate of the number of hours per week)
15. How often do you receive feedback/comments after submitting an application or proposal?
16. Do you lack confidence or face language/communication barriers when approaching funders?
17. Do you think the size of your organization impacts your ability to receive grants?
18. Do you think you have achieved the ideal organizational capacity to receive grants?
19. Does a third party audit your finances?
20. If yes above, how often are your financials audited?
21. How often does your organization not meet the gender requirements for grants?

22. How often do you keep staff on temporary or yearly contracts due to funding issues or project durations?
23. How often do you believe your organization is excluded because of a lack of "innovation" element in your project(s)?
24. Do you face challenges quantifying the impacts of your projects for grant applications?
25. Do you face local governmental barriers (rules or laws) that limit the grants or funders you can work with?
26. What percentage of the grants you have received are through open calls?
27. What percentage of the grants you have received are through networking or connections?
28. How do you define a "locally led" organization?
29. What other barriers do you often face when trying to access funding from international funders and donors?

9.4 Appendix D - Funder Survey Questions

1. What is the percentage breakdown of funding for local, regional, and international organizations?
 - a. Answer format: multiple choice box: local, regional, international each a line with associated percentages (0, 25, 50, 75, 100) and other.
2. Do you only fund water projects in a specific technical area (ex drinking water)?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
3. What are your eligibility requirements for grant recipients?
 - a. Answer format: text box
4. Do you have different requirements for local, regional, and international organizations?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
5. What size projects do you fund?
 - a. Answer format: multiple choice with multiple selection options (< \$50,000, \$50,000-\$100,000, \$100,000-\$250,000) \$250,000 +)
6. How long are the projects you fund?
 - a. Answer format: multiple choice with multiple selection options (< 3 months, 3-6 months, 6-12 months, 1-2 years, 2+ years)
7. What are the most common reasons organizations are disqualified?
 - a. Answer format: text box
8. Do you have requirements to be considered a local organization?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation

9. On average how many applicants do you receive for each grant call?
 - a. Answer format: text box
10. Does your organization have goals for allocating funding or a percentage of your portfolio to locally led organizations?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
11. Does your organization have gender equity requirements for grant recipients? If so, what are the requirements?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
12. What are the biggest obstacles to granting funding to local organizations?
 - a. Answer format: text box
13. Do you disqualify locally led organizations that have an international entity?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
14. Do you have requirements for financial documentation and audits?
 - a. Answer format: Yes/No, optional text box for explanation
15. What is your application process? Please paste the URL link if available.
 - a. Answer format: text box
16. How often do you accept grant applications?
 - a. Answer format: text box
17. Where do you post your calls for grant applications and are they promoted on any mailing lists?
 - a. Answer format: text box